

Unraveling the genetic Code: Pharmacogenomics' Role in personalized Drug Responses

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Publication history: Received on 21st October; Revised on 18th November; Accepted on 22nd November

Article DOI:

Abstract: The purpose of this review is to shed light on the intricate relationship between an individual's genetic make-up and their response to medicine. As we investigate this complex field, we aim to pinpoint the different ways that genetic variations affect the safety and effectiveness of pharmacological treatments. Knowing How Genetics Affect Drug Reaction, Pharmacogenomics is based on the detection of genetic differences in the transporters, receptors, and enzymes that the body uses to metabolize drugs. These differences greatly increase the inter-individual variability in pharmaceutical metabolism, which results in minute differences in the efficacy and toxicity of medications. This section highlights how important it is to comprehend these. This review delves into the potentially transformative effects of pharmacogenomic testing in the context of personalized medicine. By understanding some patient's genetic code, these tests offer a singular opportunity to customize drug therapy to their genetic profile. This not only improves the efficacy of therapy but also lowers the possibility of negative side effects, which aligns with the principles of customized medicine. As a result, this study successfully navigates the challenging area of pharmacogenomics and highlights how it has a significant impact on changing how we treat patients with medications. Better patient care as well as improved treatment results might result from the discoveries made in this field.

Keywords: Pharmacogenomics; Genetic code; Genetic variation; Personalized medicine; Pharmacogenomic testing; Customized drug therapy

1. Introduction

Pharmacogenomics (PGx) is the study of how genetic variation in an individual's reaction to medication occurs. It is the newest branch of medicine and is rapidly developing as a field of study. The pharmaceutical business is learning how to apply it, include it into the process of developing new drugs, and better handle the demands of the medical community [1]. The study of different genomic data, such as polymorphisms, gene expression, copy number, methylation, and protein profiles, to determine how differently medications react to patients is known as pharmacogenomics [2]. The use of genetics to enhance drug research and development is referred to as pharmacogenomics. The phrase "tailored medicine" often refers to the process of creating the appropriate medication for the appropriate patient. The combination of molecular pharmacology and functional genomics is known as personalised medicine [3].

The goal of pharmacogenomics is to identify and interpret relationships between a patient's genotypes, or genetic profile, and how well they respond to treatment. These correlations are used by pharmacogenomics to find novel, highly effective treatments based on a patient's genetic composition [4]. The procedure entails first determining which genes and the protein progeny they produce are suitable targets for drugs, and then figuring out how each gene varies. Growing evidence that an individual's genetic profile is and will continue to be the primary predictor of how effective specific medicines are has sparked interest in and financing for pharmacogenomics [5]. The procedure entails first determining which genes and the protein progeny they produce are suitable targets for drugs, and then figuring out how each gene varies. Additionally, there is a chance that personalised therapy will lead to

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better health outcomes and lower healthcare costs. Our genes contain inherent differences known as DNA polymorphisms that influence our susceptibility to certain diseases [6].

2. Individual Genetic Composition

Pharmacogenomics offers hope that medications may eventually be customised to a person's unique genetic composition. A person's response to medication can be influenced by their environment, food, age, lifestyle, and health, but it is believed that knowing a person's genetic composition will be essential to developing tailored medications that are more effective, and safe [7]. Introduction Drug response varies from person to person; there is no one-size-fits-all solution. This is the main driving force for customised healthcare. Adverse drug responses (ADRs) and variations in drug responsiveness between populations are frequent occurrences [8]. ADRs also represent a serious threat to public health since these unexpected drug response side effects might not only make patients worse but also have a substantial financial impact on the hospitalisation rate associated with ADRs [9,10]. Individual differences in genetic makeup have been demonstrated to determine an individual's risk of having any disease as well as their potential response to prescribed medication and environmental circumstances. This makes genetic composition a predictable element [11, 12]. Furthermore, numerous genes rather than a single gene mutation cause diversity in the medication response in a disease [13].

2.1 Genetic Diversity:

Finding genetic variations that alter organismal phenotypes has long been the focus of genetic studies. Comparing the mean phenotypic differences between genotypes is a common method for doing this. Despite mounting evidence supporting genetic regulation of phenotypic variance in a number of species [14,15,16]. Variation differences in phenotypes have not received much attention. However, the realisation that phenotypic variance depends on genotype has spurred the discovery of genetic variants linked to phenotypic variability in recent time [17,18]. One of the main reasons why different people react differently to medications and other xenobiotics is variation in the human DNA. Genetic variation plays a role in determining one's susceptibility to nearly all diseases [19]. A significant clinical impact results from the existence of genetic variations influencing a large number of genes expressed in hepatocytes. This article provides a comprehensive overview of the most significant gene variations involved in detoxification processes; however, it is not a full list [20]. Several groups have chosen to concentrate on researching the genetic basis of medication response because an individual's genetic composition remains stable throughout their life. While pharmacogenomics primarily studies these variants on a genome-wide scale, the term "pharmacogenetics" is now widely used in the postgenomic era to refer to the study of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) or other types of genetic variants that are associated with differences in drug response [21].

There are genetic variations throughout populations worldwide, and these variations are frequently linked to the disparities in pharmacological responses amongst populations. Focusing on these drug-response genes is an excellent place to start in pharmacogenetics because drug response is significantly influenced by genes in the drug pharmacokinetic (PK) and pharmacodynamic (PD) pathways. Finding the SNPs will be possible once these PK and PD genes have been discovered, particularly those with notable variations in population frequencies. It may be possible to utilise these population-differentiated SNPs as genetic markers to anticipate variations in medication response among populations [22].

3. Pharmacogenomics

Pharmacogenomics and pharmacogenetics study how a person's genetic makeup affects how they react to medications. Pharmacogenomics takes the whole genome into account, whereas pharmacogenetics concentrates on particular gene variants. These disciplines, which came into being in the 1950s, integrate pharmacology, biochemistry, and genetics under the umbrella of pharmacogenetics. Despite advancements, population-based statistics are still frequently used in modern medicine to forecast the specific treatment results that will inform drug selection and dose. This demonstrates how medicine continues to rely on broad techniques [23]. Information about how human genetic diversity affects pharmacological responses is gathered and shared through the Pharmacogenomics Knowledgebase. It provides information that is pertinent to clinical settings, including suggested dosage regimens, label annotations, and possible gene-drug correlations. This validates the idea of "individualised medicine," which Sir William Osler anticipated in the late 1800s, acknowledging the substantial individual variation in drug reactions [24]. Personalized medicine heavily relies on genetics, especially in the area of pharmacogenomics. This entails selecting drugs and determining dosages according to a person's genetic makeup. Pharmacogenomic differences have a substantial impact on drug safety and efficacy, prompting international scientific bodies to formulate treatment guidelines. Interestingly, groups like the Dutch Pharmacogenetics Working Group (DPWG) and the Clinical Pharmacogenetics Implementation Consortium (CPIC) have produced validated guidelines for a variety of drug-gene interactions, offering a freely available online resource for clinical application [25]. The aim of precision medicine is to precisely match the patient's molecular profile with each treatment intervention. Modern sequencing technology have revolutionised the field of human genetics over the past 20 years, advancing our knowledge of the connection between genetic diversity and human health [26]

3.1. Gene Therapy

Gene therapy is generally understood to be the transfer of genetic material with the goal of curing an illness or at the very least improving a patient's clinical condition. Transforming viruses into genetic shuttles that would transfer the desired gene into the target cells is one of the fundamental ideas of gene therapy. To do this, safe techniques utilising a variety of viral and non-viral vectors have been developed [27].

Gene therapy, also known as human gene transfer, is a branch of medicine that focuses on using therapeutic nucleic acid delivery into patient cells as a medication to treat disease [28, 29]. Martin Cline made the first attempt to alter human DNA in 1980, but it wasn't until May 1989 that the National Institutes of Health authorised the first successful nuclear gene transfer in humans [30].

Treatment for a variety of inherited or acquired hematologic illnesses may be possible with gene therapy. It entails either introducing a therapeutic gene to provide a missing or faulty protein or introducing a functional gene to replace a mutant one. Hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs), in instance, are extracted from patients and used in experiments outside of the body in some situations. These targeted cells are given the therapeutic genes by means of a vector. Ex vivo gene therapy is then carried out by reintroducing the altered cells into the patient. With the ability to modify cells outside of the body prior to reinfusion, this technique presents a promising therapeutic option [31]. The unit of inheritance is the gene. A gene is a section of DNA that codes for the creation of a particular kind of RNA or protein. It can be described as a section of DNA that controls the expression and inheritance of a specific trait. In 1995, Seymour Benzer coined the terms "cistron, muton, and recon."

Cistron: (Unit of function is in charge of a trait's expression. It is a section of DNA with instructions needed to synthesize a certain protein or RNA. It may span several hundred base pairs.

Muton: (Unit of mutation). There are a few nucleotides in it (one to few bp long). It is a section of DNA that is mutable.

Recon: (Unit of recombination). It is a specific DNA segment that crosses over during meiosis during recombination. It is made up of several base pairs [32].

Treatments for terminal diseases that were previously only temporary have been made possible through gene therapy. While effective and long-term cured instances have been reported recently, gene therapy has not been successful for a long time. A wide range of hereditary ailments, such as blood abnormalities, immunological deficiencies, vision issues, nerve cell regeneration, metabolic disorders, and different forms of cancer, have shown encouraging outcomes [33]. Methods, kinds, and vectors Gene-based treatments, often known as gene therapy, are essentially described as adding exogenous nucleic acids to rectify defective genes or change the expression of certain genes in order to prevent, halt, or reverse a pathological process[34]. When performing gene therapy, three main strategies are used. The most popular method, known as gene addition/insertion, is inserting a functioning copy of a defective gene that would ordinarily produce a crucial protein into cells. It has been demonstrated that this approach can treat hereditary conditions including haemophilia and cystic fibrosis [35,36]. Gene therapy is used to treat conditions involving the absence of particular proteins, like a chloride channel or clotting factor IX. One method involves introducing the genes encoding these proteins into cells, causing the patient's deficient protein to be expressed. RNA interference with double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) is another technique for gene knockdown (RNAi). Target messenger RNA (mRNA) is bound by RNAi, which causes mRNA degradation and suppresses the expression of the mutant gene. For therapeutic purposes, both strategies seek to correct genetic deficits and restore or control protein levels [34, 37].

3.2. Personalized medicine

Not unexpectedly, the discipline of pharmacogenetics is particularly receptive to the idea of individualization [38], the genetic analysis of a person to influence prescription and dose modifications for medications. Recent instances indicate how medications are marketed for certain demographics; for instance, the US Food and Drug Administration specifically authorised BiDil as a therapy for heart failure among African Americans, [39,40] Only a limited group of CF patients are eligible to use ivacaftor. Despite this, it's probably impractical to think about prescribing drugs to each individual based on their unique genotype. Initially, the development of drugs is not a charitable endeavour; pharmaceutical companies have a financial stake in seeing a return on their investment. There will only be a limited number of medications in development at any given moment due to the expenditures associated with drug development. While actual amounts spent on drug research have grown over the past ten years, recent data indicates,[41] Since fewer new medications are entering the market, the price of each drug that is marketed has gone up [42]. Over 30 million prescriptions for warfarin (Coumadin), an anticoagulant, have been written in the US alone [43] Warfarin is a useful therapy for thrombotic episodes, but it has a minor risk of significant bleeding that might be fatal. On a scale known as the International Normalized Ratio (INR), which compares the blood's clotting propensity to that of a reference population, the likelihood of such unfavourable outcomes is increased. Maintaining the dosage of warfarin within the optimal range—which is high enough to prevent thrombotic events but low enough to save patients from an excessively high risk of side effects—is challenging when administering the medication. The fact that there is a lot of inter-individual diversity in the way people metabolise warfarin contributes to this challenge from the standpoint of genetics [43,44]

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, by customising medicines to each patient's unique genetic makeup, the sciences of pharmacogenomics and gene therapy show enormous promise to transform medicine. Considerable progress has been made toward customised healthcare with the introduction of personalised medicine and the incorporation of genetic data into medication development procedures. Notwithstanding obstacles, persistent endeavours and an expanding comprehension of genetic modifications furnish a sturdy basis for the sustained advancement of customized healthcare. Genetics will have a revolutionary influence on healthcare in the future because of its capacity to maximise therapeutic efficacy, reduce adverse medication reactions, and improve health outcomes.

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